

【Article】

Criticism of Mass Media and Vested Interests,
Moral Psychology, and Non-Minority Politics:
Underlying Currents of the Ishimaru
and Saito Phenomena in Japan

Tadamasa, KIMURA[†]

Abstract

This paper analyzes the "Ishimaru phenomenon" and "Saito phenomenon" in Japanese local elections in 2024, which captured significant attention from the mass media and Japanese society at large, examining factors influencing candidate selection through a 2024 web survey. The study reveals a significant critical attitude towards mass media and vested interests and a decline in their trust as key drivers. Moreover, this criticism is strongly motivated by moral psychological factors and "non-minority politics," a pervasive resentment toward minorities which the author has found as a distinctive feature of Japanese online public opinion discourse.

Keywords: Criticism of mass media and vested interests, Moral psychology, Non-minority politics, Ishimaru and Saito phenomena, Japanese society

1. Introduction

The year 2024 witnessed two notable events in Japanese local politics that captured significant attention from the mass media and Japanese society at large: the remarkable performance of Shinji Ishimaru, a relatively unknown independent candidate, in the Tokyo gubernatorial election, and the tumultuous situation surrounding Hyogo Prefecture Governor Saito, who faced allegations of power harassment, subjected to a unanimous no-confidence vote by the prefectural assembly, only to be re-elected in a subsequent gubernatorial election.

These two distinct scenarios offer a compelling lens through which to examine contemporary

[†]Professor, College of Sociology, Rikkyo University

Japanese political dynamics, the evolving role of media in shaping public perception, and the factors influencing electoral outcomes at the local level.

One distinctive commonality is the significant influence of social media platforms such as X (formerly Twitter), YouTube, and TikTok (collectively referred to here as SNS) and online strategies in both cases. Both Ishimaru and Saito, in different ways, leveraged online platforms to connect with voters, disseminate their messages, and potentially bypass traditional media narratives.

Another shared element is the role of anti-establishment sentiment and voter discontent. Ishimaru's campaign explicitly tapped into this sentiment, criticizing "vested interests" and appealing to voters seeking change. In Saito's case, his supporters embraced a narrative that the power harassment allegations were a media fabrication, and that the resignation drama was a "coup" orchestrated by vested interests opposed to his reforms, suggesting a similar underlying dissatisfaction with the status quo, albeit framed differently.

As a researcher who has specialized in the relationship between the internet and socio-cultural change since the mid-1990s—particularly in the fields of network society theory and media communication—and who has focused over the past decade on the dynamics of “online public opinion,” I conducted a web-based survey in December 2024 to examine whether the theoretical perspectives developed in that research could be used to interpret the political developments of that year.

The findings offer fresh insights into the broader discourse surrounding the so-called Ishimaru and Saito phenomena. Accordingly, this paper seeks to reinterpret these phenomena in light of the December 2024 survey (hereafter “the survey”), using the conceptual framework developed in my earlier work.

2. Survey Design and Overview of Gubernatorial Candidates

The survey was conducted from December 2 to 4, 2024, targeting respondents aged 20–69 living in the Tokyo metropolitan area (Tokyo, Kanagawa, Saitama, Chiba), Osaka, Hyogo, and Aichi prefectures. The sample consisted of 2,000 participants, proportionally allocated by region and evenly stratified by age (in 10-year intervals) and gender: 1,250 from the Tokyo area, 300 from Osaka, 200 from Hyogo, and 250 from Aichi.

To ensure data quality, responses were screened for inattentiveness or insincerity. After excluding unreliable responses, 1,678 were retained for analysis. The proportion of invalid responses did not vary significantly by gender, age group, or region.

This paper investigates the factors that influenced participants' hypothetical choices for the Tokyo and Hyogo gubernatorial elections. Rather than asking participants whom they actually

voted for, the survey asked them to imagine voting as of early December 2024—well after the elections had taken place and amid evolving media narratives around each candidate. Importantly, this approach includes responses from people who were not eligible to vote in those elections (due to location or other factors), thereby allowing for an analysis of broader public perceptions of the candidates.

For the Tokyo election, respondents were asked to choose from among the seven candidates who had received over 100,000 votes, plus Sakurai, who is a political activist well known for his far-right nationalist views. For the Hyogo election, the top five candidates were listed. In both cases, options such as “Other,” “Blank/Abstained,” and “Prefer not to answer” were included. Notably, although non-response and abstention were frequent, the distribution of candidate choices was broadly similar between those who reported voting and those who did not.

When comparing the distribution of candidate preferences in this survey to the actual election outcomes (see Table 1), we observe that Renhō received only about half the level of support she garnered in the real Tokyo gubernatorial election. In contrast, candidates with a strong presence on the internet—such as Anno, Himazora, and Sakurai—received slightly higher levels of support. Similarly, in the Hyogo gubernatorial race, Tachibana’s support was relatively high, while Shimizu and Ōsawa were underrepresented. These patterns likely reflect biases inherent in web-based survey panels.

Support for Koike and Inamura was approximately 10% higher than in the actual election; however, with regard to the two focal figures of this study—Ishimaru and Saitō—the levels of support were almost identical to real-world results.

Table 1. Distribution of Candidate Support in the Survey vs. Actual Election Results

Tokyo Gubernatorial Election				Hyogo Gubernatorial Election			
Candidates/ other choices	Number of Survey Respondents	Share Among 8 Candidates (Survey)	Share Among 8 Candidates (Official Results)	Candidates/ other choices	Number of Survey Respondents	Share Among 5 Candidates (Survey)	Share Among 5 Candidates (Official Results)
KOIKE	407	50.0%	44.2%	SAITŌ	267	44.9%	45.6%
ISHIMARU	221	27.1%	25.1%	INAMURA	257	43.3%	40.0%
RENHŌ	80	9.8%	19.5%	SHIMIZU	36	6.1%	10.6%
TAMOGAMI	34	4.2%	4.1%	TACHIBANA	25	4.2%	0.8%
ANNO	23	2.8%	2.3%	ŌSAWA	9	1.5%	3.0%
HIMAZORA	20	2.5%	1.7%	<i>Other Candidates</i>	44	—	—
SAKURAI	19	2.3%	1.3%	<i>Blank/Abstained</i>	511	—	—
UTSUMI	10	1.2%	1.8%	<i>No Response</i>	529	—	—
<i>Other Candidates</i>	30	—	—				
<i>Blank/Abstained</i>	349	—	—				
<i>No Response</i>	485	—	—				

3. Analytical Model: Factors Influencing Candidate Selection

Building on the overview of candidates and voting patterns, this study investigates the underlying factors that influenced respondents' choices using multinomial logistic regression. The dependent variable is candidate selection in either the Tokyo or Hyogo gubernatorial election. The analysis draws on 804 valid responses for the Tokyo election (excluding Utsumi) and 594 for the Hyogo election (excluding Osawa).

Table 2 outlines the independent variables used in the analysis. Basic socioeconomic characteristics (10 items, such as gender and age) are straightforward and not elaborated upon here. Other variables critical to this analysis are briefly explained below.

One core hypothesis is that the rise of Ishimaru and Saito reflects a transformation in the media landscape, wherein individuals now engage with political content through platforms that bypass traditional media. Accordingly, the survey included 20 items assessing political information engagement—such as posting, sharing, and browsing—across different media. Factor analysis revealed five distinct dimensions. Although Factor 5 (engagement with TV and newspapers) had relatively low internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.397$), it was retained for theoretical relevance. Media sources such as Facebook, LINE News, radio, and news apps did not align with any of the five factors and were excluded from the regression.

Table 2: Independent Variables in the Regression Analysis

Category	Factors and question items
Socioeconomic Attributes	Gender, Age, Household Income, Education Level, Employment Type, Perceived Living Standard, Life Satisfaction, Marital Status, Presence of Children, Prefecture of Residence
Political Information Behavior:	<i>Factor 1: Posting/Sharing</i> – reposting on X, posting on X, commenting on Yahoo! News, the largest online media outlet in Japan, and commenting on other online news platforms.
	<i>Factor 2: SNS/Video Engagement</i> – browsing general internet content, X (Twitter), video content, and social media.
	<i>Factor 3: Online Public Sphere Participation</i> – browsing forums such as 5ch, Japanese forum thread aggregators, portals, online news platforms and blogs
	<i>Factor 4: Yahoo News Browsing</i> – frequency of viewing Yahoo News and its comment sections
	<i>Factor 5: Mass Media Exposure</i> – watching TV, reading newspapers
Trust in Information Sources	<i>Mass Media Trust:</i> TV, newspapers, radio
	<i>Online News Trust:</i> Yahoo News, news apps
	<i>SNS/Video Trust:</i> X (Twitter), video platforms, social media, online influencers
Flaming Behavior Online	<i>Active Flaming:</i> initiating or correcting misinformation in online flame wars; since this factor is highly skewed, with a small number of active respondents and a majority indicating little to no involvement, a log-transformed score for active flaming was used.
	<i>Flaming Interest:</i> observing or monitoring flame-related incidents
Echo Chamber Exposure	Following the methodology developed for the World Internet Project and prior studies (Dubois and Blank 2018; Dutton et al. 2019), the survey measures exposure to opposing viewpoints, separated into traditional and online media domains
Criticism of Mass Media and Vested Interests	Six items measuring critical attitudes toward media bias, collusion with vested interests, and uncritical media trust
Moral Foundations Theory (MFT)	<i>Ingroup Loyalty:</i> patriotism, detecting betrayal, obedience to authority, adherence to tradition
	<i>Respect for Tradition:</i> endorsement of traditional gender roles and historical values

Social Dominance Orientation (SDO)	Based on SDO7 (Ho et al. 2015), four items indicating support for hierarchical social structures and opposition to group-based equality.
Self-Esteem	Three items from Rosenberg’s Self-Esteem Scale (Rosenberg 1965, Uchida and Ueno 2010)
Contempt for Others	Three items assessing disdain for the ignorance or arrogance of others
Virtual Competence Type (VTC)	Combining self-esteem and contempt levels, respondents were categorized in terms of competence type as: <i>Omnipotent</i> (high self-esteem, high contempt); <i>Virtual</i> (low self-esteem, high contempt); <i>Self-Esteem Type</i> (high self-esteem, low contempt); <i>Withdrawn</i> (low self-esteem, low contempt)
Political Orientation	Self-placement on a 7-point ideological spectrum between right-wing and left-wing, with a “no answer” option
Non-Minority Politics	Agreement with a statement criticizing perceived minority overreach in claiming special rights

To assess trust in political information sources, respondents were asked to rate the trustworthiness of ten different media channels they personally use—ranging from television and Twitter to family, friends, and acquaintances. A factor analysis (with Quartimin oblique rotation) of these ten items revealed a two-factor structure, as shown in Table 3.

When examining the internal consistency (Cronbach’s alpha) of these factors, higher reliability was achieved by narrowing each set: For Factor 1 (mass media trust), excluding news apps and retaining the remaining four items yielded $\alpha = 0.882$. For Factor 2 (network-based sources), excluding Yahoo! News and using the other three items yielded $\alpha = 0.862$.

In practical terms, Yahoo! News and news apps are hybrid in nature. While they are digitally accessed and resemble online platforms, their content largely originates from traditional mass media. Therefore, they are perceived differently from SNS or video-sharing apps.

Based on these distinctions, trust in information sources was categorized into three groups (as shown in Table 2):

- Mass Media Trust: newspapers, television, radio
- Online News Trust: Yahoo! News, news apps
- SNS/Video Trust: X (formerly Twitter), video platforms, social media, online influencers

This threefold classification was deemed most appropriate for analytical purposes.

Table 3: Factor Analysis – Trust in Information Sources

Factor	Items	Loadings	Factor	Items	Loadings
Factor 1 (SNS-based Trust)	SNS	0.853	Factor 2 (Mass Media Trust)	Newspapers	0.896
	Twitter (X)	0.826		TV	0.844
	Video platforms	0.825		Radio	0.785
	Online influencers	0.764		Yahoo News	0.558
	News apps	0.456		Family conversation	0.290

Eigenvalues: 4.47 (F1), 2.12 (F2); Variance Explained: 34.7% (F1), 31.5% (F2)

My previous research has examined the role of moral psychology in shaping online political engagement, focusing on three key theoretical constructs: Moral Foundations Theory (MFT), Social Dominance Orientation (SDO), and Virtual Type Competence (VTC). MFT, originally developed by Haidt and colleagues (e.g., Haidt 2012), posits that moral judgments are not primarily driven by logical reasoning but rather by evolved emotional mechanisms that suppress selfish behavior and promote altruism and cooperation within social groups.

People make everyday moral evaluations—e.g., good vs. evil, truth vs. falsehood—not through abstract rationality but through intuitive responses rooted in multiple foundational values. These include individualistic values like *care/harm* (e.g., empathy, anger at cruelty) and *fairness/cheating* (e.g., concern for justice, condemnation of double standards), as well as collectivistic values such as *ingroup loyalty* (e.g., pride in one’s group, anger at betrayal) and *respect for tradition/authority* (e.g., adherence to social norms, moral condemnation of deviance).

My research has shown that *ingroup loyalty* and *respect for authority*, as conceptualized in MFT, are particularly influential in motivating political and social engagement online—such as sharing, commenting, and amplifying political content. Accordingly, the present survey included eight items from the Moral Foundations Questionnaire (MFQ), divided into two subscales: *ingroup loyalty* (4 items) and *respect for tradition/authority* (3 items), as summarized in Table 2.

Social Dominance Orientation (SDO) is another key psychological construct, which accounts for generalized prejudice across social categories such as race, gender, sexuality, religion, and disability (Ho et al. 2012). SDO reflects a worldview in which social life is seen as a competition among groups, legitimizing intergroup hierarchies and dominance over outgroups (Pratto et al. 1994). My earlier findings suggest that higher SDO is associated with greater expression of online political opinions and participation in polarizing online discourse.

Virtual Type Competence (VTC) draws on the concept of *assumed competence* developed by Toshihiko Hayami and colleagues in the 2000s. Their work responded to public discourse on “short-tempered youth” who, despite low self-esteem, displayed strong contempt for others—expressed through attitudes like “most people are incompetent” or “people pretend to know things they don’t.” Hayami framed this pattern as *assumed competence*, linking it to youth who were emotionally reactive and quick to anger. He also developed the scheme of four types of perceived competence, combining self-esteem and contempt for others described in Table 2. While he uses the term *Assumed Competence Scale (ACS)*, I do not endorse the “short-tempered youth” narrative; thus, I refer to it here as *virtual type competence (VTC)* for analytical clarity. My earlier research shows that the *virtual type* is most strongly associated with active participation in online opinion dynamics and flaming behavior.

This survey included three items to measure self-esteem and three for contempt for others, and calculated average scores for each. Based on the total score (median = 11, average ~10), respondents were dichotomized into “high” (11+) and “low” (10 or below) groups for each dimension. The four VTC types were then classified as categorical variables in the regression model (see Table 2).

Finally, Non-Minority Politics, a concept I developed in earlier work (Kimura 2017), captures a distinctive feature of Japanese online discourse: a pervasive resentment toward minorities. Rather than asserting majoritarian interests explicitly, users often express the belief that they themselves are not receiving adequate benefits, while minorities are exploiting their status to gain special rights or compensation.

This discourse frames criticism of foreigners, gender minorities, persons with disabilities, ethnic minorities, juvenile protections, welfare recipients, or even parents with strollers not as isolated prejudices but as a unified narrative of resentment. Terms like “victim business,” “welfare freeloading,” or “public funds siphoning” illustrate this worldview, which opposes liberal or identity-based minority politics with sarcastic or hostile counter-rhetoric.

To capture this sentiment, the survey included an original question item assessing agreement with the belief that “so-called minorities exploit their vulnerability to claim rights and receive benefits.” This was used as the indicator for non-minority politics.

4. Diverging Bases of Support: Distinctions and Overlaps Between Ishimaru and Saitō Voters

Using the variables described in the previous section as independent variables and candidate choice as the dependent variable, we conducted a multinomial logistic regression analysis. Table 4 summarizes the variables that were statistically significant at the 5% level ($p < 0.05$). The Tokyo election analysis included seven candidates, and the Hyogo election included four; thus, the variables shown are not necessarily significant predictors for selecting Ishimaru or Saitō specifically. That said, examining how each variable relates to different candidates reveals meaningful contrasts. However, since this paper primarily focuses on Ishimaru and Saitō, the following analysis will concentrate on the most relevant points for interpreting their support bases. For clarity, we refer to candidates by name, which denotes “respondents who selected that candidate.”

We begin by reviewing the overlap in candidate selections between the Tokyo and Hyogo gubernatorial elections, as shown in Table 5. The table includes only those who selected a candidate and excludes responses such as “Other,” “Blank/Abstained,” and “Prefer not to answer.”

Table 4. Regression Results for Candidate Selection (Variables Significant at the 5% Level)

Tokyo Gubernatorial Election			Hyogo Gubernatorial Election		
Variables	Log Odds	p-value	Variables	Log Odds	p-value
Criticism of Mass Media and Vested Interest	4.657	0.000	Trust in Information Sources (Mass Media Trust)	4.401	0.000
Trust in Information Sources (Mass Media Trust)	4.547	0.000	Active Flaming Behavior (log-transformed)	2.201	0.006
Political Info Behavior – Factor 4 (Yahoo! News Use)	2.589	0.003	Trust in Information Sources (SNS/Video Trust)	2.159	0.007
Contempt for Others	2.583	0.003	Contempt for Others	2.094	0.008
Gender	2.544	0.003	Prefecture of Residence	1.663	0.022
Political Orientation (Right–Left)	2.182	0.007	Political Orientation (Right–Left)	1.559	0.028
Political Info Behavior – Factor 5 (Mass Media Use)	1.526	0.030	Marital Status	1.463	0.034
			Criticism of Mass Media and Vested Interest	1.404	0.039
			Trust in Information Sources (Online News Trust)	1.356	0.044

Model Fit: Entropy $R^2 = 0.32$ (Tokyo), 0.50 (Hyogo)

The table shows that nearly 65% of those who selected Ishimaru also selected Saitō. Similarly, 40% of Koike supporters and over 50% of Tamogami, Himazora, and Sakurai supporters also selected Saitō—Himazora being the highest at just under 70%. In other words, while a large portion of Ishimaru supporters also chose Saitō, many who did not select Ishimaru also favored Saitō.

From the perspective of the Hyogo gubernatorial election shown in Table 6, Saitō’s support base is more evenly split between those who selected Koike and those who selected Ishimaru in the Tokyo election. Thus, we cannot assume a one-to-one correspondence between support for Ishimaru and Saitō. It is therefore essential to analyze both their differences and similarities carefully, especially in relation to other candidates.

Table 5. Distribution of Hyogo Gubernatorial Candidate Preferences by Tokyo Gubernatorial Candidate Choice (%)

Choice of Tokyo Election	Share Among 5 Hyogo Candidates				
	SAITŌ	INAMURA	SHIMIZU	TACHIBANA	ŌSAWA
KOIKE	39.0	52.1	6.4	2.1	0.4
ISHIMARU	64.6	27.2	2.0	6.1	0.0
RENHŌ	12.1	74.1	6.9	0.0	6.9
TAMOGAMI	50.0	21.4	17.9	10.7	0.0
ANNO	26.7	46.7	13.3	6.7	6.7
HIMAZORA	69.2	15.4	7.7	7.7	0.0
SAKURAI	58.3	8.3	8.3	25.0	0.0
Total(N=470)	44.3	43.8	6.6	4.3	1.1

Table 6. Distribution of Tokyo Gubernatorial Candidate Preferences by Hyogo Gubernatorial Candidate Choice (%)

Choice of Hyogo Election	Share Among 8 Tokyo Candidates							
	KOIKE	ISHIMARU	RENHŌ	TAMOGAMI	ANNO	HIMAZORA	SAKURAI	UTSUMI
SAITŌ	39.5	40.8	3.0	6.0	1.7	3.9	3.0	2.1
INAMURA	55.2	17.9	19.3	2.7	3.1	0.9	0.4	0.4
SHIMIZU	48.4	9.7	12.9	16.1	6.5	3.2	3.2	0.0
TACHIBANA	20.8	37.5	0.0	12.5	4.2	4.2	12.5	8.3
Total(N=472)	46.0	28.6	10.4	5.5	3.0	2.5	2.5	1.5

When examining the socioeconomic attributes listed in Table 2, variables such as educational attainment, employment/occupation, and household income did not show significant effects in either the Tokyo or Hyogo gubernatorial elections. However, gender emerged as a statistically significant factor in the Tokyo election. To explore this further, Table 7 summarizes the gender-age group distribution by candidate.

Table 7. Gender-Age Distribution by Selected Candidate (%)

Candidates	F20s	F30s	F40s	F50s	F60s	M20s	M30s	M40s	M50s	M60s
KOIKE	8.1	8.4	10.6	10.1	13.8	7.9	8.4	9.8	9.6	13.5
ISHIMARU	6.3	6.3	5.9	4.1	9.5	14.9	17.7	16.3	8.6	10.4
RENHŌ	12.5	10.0	5.0	6.3	15.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	13.8	22.5
TAMOGAMI	0.0	5.9	5.9	14.7	2.9	17.7	11.8	5.9	20.6	14.7
ANNO	8.7	4.4	0.0	4.4	4.4	30.4	13.0	4.4	8.7	21.7
HIMAZORA	5.0	5.0	15.0	5.0	0.0	10.0	25.0	20.0	15.0	0.0
SAKURAI	5.3	10.5	10.5	10.5	5.3	5.3	5.3	10.5	15.8	21.1
Tokyo Total	7.6	7.7	8.3	8.0	11.4	10.6	11.2	11.1	10.5	13.7
SAITŌ	8.6	8.2	8.2	6.0	9.4	10.9	13.9	13.5	12.4	9.0
INAMURA	5.1	5.5	5.8	9.3	13.2	4.3	6.2	12.1	15.2	23.4
SHIMIZU	8.3	5.6	8.3	8.3	0.0	30.6	16.7	5.6	5.6	11.1
TACHIBANA	4.0	4.0	8.0	0.0	0.0	20.0	24.0	28.0	4.0	8.0
Hyogo Total	6.8	6.7	7.2	7.4	10.1	9.6	11.1	13.0	12.8	15.4

While the overall sample was stratified evenly by gender and age group, among those who selected one of the seven Tokyo candidates or the four Hyogo candidates, the distribution was skewed: men outnumbered women, and respondents in their 60s were disproportionately represented. This suggests that candidate choice may be partially influenced by demographic bias.

Looking at Table 7 with this in mind, we observe that Saitō attracted a relatively high proportion of both men and women in their 20s to 40s, with a particularly notable presence among women. In contrast, Inamura was more frequently chosen by men and women in their 50s and 60s, and had relatively few male supporters in their 20s or 30s.

Ishimaru's support also skewed toward younger men—nearly 50% of his supporters were males

in their 20s to 40s. However, support among women was limited, accounting for only about one-third of his total supporters. Renhō, like Inamura, had very few male supporters in their 20s or 30s.

5. Strong Criticism of Media Elites and Trust in Information Sources

Two factors—**criticism of mass media and vested interests** and **trust in mass media**—were significant predictors of candidate selection in both the Tokyo and Hyogo elections.

The survey included a six-item scale developed in response to the Hyogo election, designed to assess respondents' attitudes toward the mass media and perceived collusion with vested interests. The items were as follows:

1. Political reform requires dismantling vested interest groups.
2. Japan's social stagnation is caused by vested elites.
3. Information from the mass media is biased and cannot be trusted.
4. The mass media are resting on the privileges of vested interests.
5. The internet reveals truths that the mass media refuse to report.
6. Most people uncritically accept what they see in the media.

Each item was designed to capture a distinct perspective. The author originally hypothesized that they reflected three domains: media criticism, anti-elite sentiment, and lack of media literacy. In the questionnaire, the six items were scattered across different sections, and the order was randomized to minimize response bias.

However, factor analysis revealed a single-factor structure (eigenvalue = 2.89, variance explained = 48.2%), with strong internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.781$). This suggests that among respondents, these seemingly distinct statements were interpreted as parts of a coherent worldview—one in which the mass media are viewed as representatives of vested interests, suspected of manipulating or concealing information, and the general public is seen as unaware of such dynamics.

Here, we defined the average of the six items (minimum = 1, maximum = 6, neutral point = 3.5) as the Criticism of Mass Media and Vested Interests Score (CMVI Score). The overall mean among all respondents was relatively high at 3.98, and notably higher among Ishimaru supporters (4.35) and Saitō supporters (4.49), indicating strong CMVI in these groups.

What is particularly interesting here is that this strong CMVI does not correlate straightforwardly with low trust in mass media or high trust in SNS and video platforms. Table 8 presents the correlation coefficients between each of the nine media sources (excluding family/friends/acquaintances) and the CMVI Score. Trust in each source was rated on a 1–6 Likert scale.

Table 8. Correlations Between Trust in Information Sources and CMVI

Information Source	Correlation Coefficient	Information Source	Correlation Coefficient
TV	-0.287	X (formerly Twitter)	0.114
Newspapers	-0.208	Video Platforms	0.112
Radio	-0.158	SNS	0.045
Yahoo! News	-0.065	Online Influencers	0.043
News Apps	-0.003		

As Table 8 shows, stronger CMVI is somehow associated with lower trust in TV and newspapers; however, the correlation coefficients remain below -0.3. While these are not negligible, the relationships are relatively weak.

Correlations between CMVI and trust in X (Twitter) or video platforms are also very weak (around 0.1), and the correlations with SNS and online influencers are nearly negligible. In other words, strong criticism of traditional media is not simply correlated with higher trust in alternative sources like X, video platforms, or social media.

To examine this more systematically, we examined the relationship between the CMVI Score and three types of trust in information sources (mass media, online news, and SNS/video), along with a mass media exposure index, across different candidate selections. The media exposure index was calculated by averaging the self-reported frequency of political information exposure from television and newspapers, coded as follows: “several times a day” = 5, “about once a day” = 4, “several times a week” = 3, “a few times a month or less” = 2, and “never” = 1. Thus, CMVI and trust scores range from 1 to 6 (with a neutral point of 3.5), while the media exposure index ranges from 1 to 5 (with a neutral point of 3.0).

Figure 1 plots the average values of these five variables, both overall and by candidate selection. The candidates are arranged from left to right in order of increasing CMVI, which coincides with decreasing levels of trust in and exposure to mass media.

Looking first at the overall sample, the average CMVI was relatively high at 3.98 (nearly 4), indicating strong criticism of mass media and vested interests. In contrast, trust in mass media averaged 3.61—slightly above the neutral point, suggesting only modest trust. Trust in online news was exactly at the neutral point, reflecting a balance between trust and distrust, while trust in SNS and video sources was notably lower, with an average of 2.86 and a median of 3, suggesting that respondents recognize the mixed reliability of such platforms and approach them with caution.

The mass media exposure index was also low, averaging 2.86, likely reflecting a broader trend of declining newspaper readership. Although not shown in the figure, political information

behavior scores indicate that the average SNS/video exposure index was also 2.86, and the Yahoo! News exposure index was 2.80—suggesting that mass media, online news, and SNS/video now exist in a roughly competitive information environment in terms of access.

When comparing candidate groups, three broad clusters emerge based on levels of media exposure:

Group 1: Koike, Renhō, Inamura, Shimizu: These candidates were supported by respondents with relatively high levels of media exposure and trust in mass media, as well as somewhat elevated trust in online news. Their average CMVI was around 4. Notably, these four candidates are affiliated with established political parties and are closely associated with legacy media (so-called “old media”).

Group 2: Anno, Ishimaru, Saitō, Tachibana, Tamogami: This group showed significantly lower trust and exposure to mass media compared to Group 1, alongside higher CMVI. Trust in online news was also somewhat lower than that of Group 1.

Group 3: Himazora, Sakurai: This group exhibited extremely limited media exposure, very low trust in mass media, and the strongest levels of CMVI.

In summary, these groups can be characterized as: (1) high exposure to and trust in mass media, (2) moderate exposure but declining trust in mass media, and (3) minimal exposure and low trust in mass media.

The second group is of particular interest to this paper. Within Group 2, from left to right in the figure, trust in mass media tends to decrease while trust in SNS/video tends to increase. However, it is not the case that Ishimaru or Saitō supporters trust SNS/video sources more than mass media. Rather, in the cases of Anno and Ishimaru, trust in mass media hovers around the neutral point, while trust in SNS/video remains at about 3—suggesting that mass media are still generally viewed as more reliable. By contrast, Tachibana and Tamogami supporters report trust in SNS/video sources that, although still below the neutral point, exceed their already low trust in mass media. Saitō appears to sit at the intersection of these two dynamics.

Figure 1. Scores overall and by candidate selection: CMVI score, Trust scores and Exposure to Mass Media index

As this analysis has shown, the Ishimaru and Saitō phenomena should not be interpreted through a simplistic binary of “mass media” versus “the internet.” Nor can they be understood as a straightforward transition or “power shift” from traditional media to online platforms. Rather, from the perspective of trust in information sources and patterns of media exposure, we observe a threefold configuration—mass media, online news, and SNS/video platforms—existing in a state of equilibrium or standoff. What drives the phenomena is not so much the rise of new media, but rather a sharp decline in trust toward mass media, coupled with strong criticism of their perceived entrenchment and influence.

As a media communication researcher, I have long been cautious about technological determinism—the assumption that new technologies directly determine social outcomes. In both the Tokyo and Hyogo gubernatorial elections, narratives easily emerged claiming that SNS and video platforms manipulated public opinion and determined electoral success. However,

technologies themselves are neutral. Historically, all sides in political and ideological conflicts—from grassroots activists to dominant powers—have harnessed the most advanced media available at the time to engage in persuasive communication and propaganda.

In the U.S. presidential context, the influence of digital media became evident during the 2004 Howard Dean campaign, and since then, actors across the political spectrum—including foreign entities—have employed diverse online tools to expand their influence. This has led to environments saturated with exaggeration, misinformation, and ambiguity between truth and falsehood.

In the recent Japanese elections, other candidates besides Ishimaru and Saitō also used the internet. Nonetheless, what set Ishimaru and Saitō apart was their ability to channel widespread dissatisfaction with media elites into a powerful online presence. This raises the question: What motivates such strong criticism and propels individuals toward participation in online discourse?

6. The Distortions of Japan’s “Lost 30 Years”: What “Contempt for Others” and “Non-Minority Politics” Reveal

6.1 MFT, SDO, and VTC as Predictors of Media Criticism

As outlined in the explanation of Table 2, my prior research suggests that three psychological constructs related to morality—Moral Foundations Theory (MFT), Social Dominance Orientation (SDO), and Virtual Type Competence (VTC)—serve as key drivers behind active engagement in online public discourse.

From this perspective, the Ishimaru and Saitō phenomena may also be shaped by these underlying moral psychologies. These psychological dispositions likely contribute to declining trust in mass media, rising criticism of vested interests, and increased use of online news, SNS, and video platforms—ultimately influencing candidate selection.

In the present survey, the only factor among these three to emerge as a significant predictor of candidate choice was Contempt for Others, a component of VTC. Other variables were not significant at the 5% level (see Table 4). So how, then, do MFT, SDO, and VTC influence candidate selection—if not directly? This study suggests that these moral psychological factors, along with Non-Minority Politics, play an indirect but significant role by contributing to CMVI.

To explore what drives CMVI, a regression analysis was conducted with CMVI as the dependent variable. The independent variables included socioeconomic attributes (from Table 2), ingroup loyalty and respect for tradition (MFT subscales), self-esteem, contempt for others (VTC), SDO, non-minority politics, and trust in SNS/video platforms. The variables that were significant at the 5% level are listed in Table 9.

The analysis revealed that socioeconomic factors (e.g., gender, age) and trust in SNS/video

were not significant predictors of CMVI. Instead, moral psychological variables—MFT, SDO, VTC—and non-minority politics were strongly associated with heightened criticism.

Table 10 summarizes the relationship between these variables and CMVI for all respondents. For explanatory variables other than socioeconomic ones, respondents were classified into four levels—high, mid-high, mid-low, and low—based on the distribution of responses. The average CMVI score was then calculated for each of these levels. As is shown in the table, across all variables, higher levels (e.g., strong ingroup loyalty, high contempt) are consistently associated with higher CMVI.

Table 9. Regression Results: Predictors of CMVI (Significant at the 5% Level)

Tokyo Gubernatorial Election			Hyogo Gubernatorial Election		
Variables	Log Odds	p-value	Variables	Log Odds	p-value
MFT: Respect for Tradition	10.91	0.000	MFT: Respect for Tradition	6.97	0.000
Contempt for Others (VTC)	6.93	0.000	Contempt for Others (VTC)	5.08	0.000
Non-Minority Politics	3.47	0.000	Non-Minority Politics	3.74	0.000
SDO	2.70	0.002	MFT: Ingroup Loyalty	1.36	0.044
Self-Esteem	1.43	0.038			

Adjusted $R^2 = 0.30$ (Tokyo), 0.28 (Hyogo)

Table 10. Average CMVI Scores by Level of MFT, SDO, VTC, and Non-Minority Politics

	high	mid-high	mid-low	low
MFT: Respect for Tradition	4.58	3.99	3.70	3.40
MFT: Ingroup Loyalty	4.61	3.95	3.81	3.55
SDO	4.49	4.05	3.84	3.58
Self-Esteem (VTC)	4.35	4.05	3.85	3.74
Contempt for Others (VTC)	4.48	4.06	3.83	3.50
Non-Minority Politics	4.52	4.05	3.86	3.66

6.2 The “Truth Default Ingroup Hypothesis” and the Moral Psychology of Intergroup Competition

Why, then, do moral-psychological traits—particularly those captured by MFT, SDO, and VTC—exert such a strong influence on CMVI, and, by extension, on the Ishimaru and Saitō phenomena?

The relationships between these psychological constructs, non-minority politics, online public discourse, and criticism of the mass media are complex, multidimensional, and layered. Fully addressing them would require a detailed anthropologically grounded framework—what I refer to as the theory of cumulative cultural learning (c.f. Henrich 2015). While I develop this argument in depth elsewhere, here I offer a brief and focused discussion relevant to the scope of

this paper.

At the core of my theoretical perspective is the idea that a defining feature of *Homo sapiens* is the adoption of an extremely high-risk survival strategy: relying on other individuals—including non-kin—for essential knowledge and skills. In this strategy, language is both an incredibly powerful asset and a potentially dangerous one. It enables efficient cooperation but also allows low-cost deception (Kimura 2024b).

For such a system to function, groups must develop mechanisms to suppress non-cooperative behavior, deceit, and betrayal, while promoting cooperation—defined as individuals willingly incurring costs to benefit others within their group. In human history, groups that failed to foster trust and cooperation likely lacked the adaptive advantage to develop cumulative culture and thus faded over time. This remains true today.

I hypothesize that human societies evolved by differentiating between “ingroup” and “outgroup” and establishing internal systems of reputation, sanctions, and social norms that made it possible for group members to assume the basic trustworthiness of each other’s words. I refer to this as the “Truth-Default Ingroup Hypothesis.”

Through this mechanism, humans developed the capacity to form large-scale social collectives—sometimes numbering in the tens or hundreds of millions—that share a coherent cultural order. To maintain such systems, people must be able to distinguish ingroup members from outsiders and rely on mechanisms such as norms, reputation, and sanctions to build and sustain trust within their group.

Furthermore, an important and sensitive issue warrants careful consideration: in order to establish and maintain a “truth-default ingroup” at the level of the nation-state, it is likely that high-cost institutions—such as bureaucracies, public education systems, and large-scale religions—have been essential. The formation and expansion of such institutions may well have been driven by intense intergroup conflict, i.e., war. While ingroup favoritism does not necessarily imply xenophobia or outgroup hatred, it is worth soberly acknowledging the possibility that group conflict has historically played a major role in enabling the development of complex, high-cost institutions that support large-scale societal structures.

Indeed, our modern world, organized around nation-states, has been built upon a worldview that interprets society through the lens of competing groups, where rhetoric of group cohesion and outgroup threat circulates widely, reinforcing national solidarity.

In this context, MFT and SDO are not merely abstract psychological concepts; they are evolved mental mechanisms that have historically supported morality and justice in human societies, and today continue to shape dynamics of online public opinion. One of the clearest expressions of this is the phenomenon of online flaming. Table 11 illustrates the relationship

between MFT, SDO, VTC and Non-Minority Politics and interest in flaming, which ranges from 1 to 6 (see Table 2). As the table shows, higher levels of moral-psychological variables are associated with greater curiosity in online flaming.

Table 11. Average Flaming Interest Scores by Level of MFT, SDO, VTC, and Non-Minority Politics

	high	mid-high	mid-low	low
MFT: Respect for Tradition	4.58	3.99	3.70	3.40
MFT: Ingroup Loyalty	4.61	3.95	3.81	3.55
SDO	4.49	4.05	3.84	3.58
Self-Esteem (VTC)	4.35	4.05	3.85	3.74
Contempt for Others (VTC)	4.48	4.06	3.83	3.50
Non-Minority Politics	4.52	4.05	3.86	3.66

Prior research on flaming has shown that a sense of “justice” or “social sanction” often motivates participation (e.g., Tanaka and Yamaguchi 2016, Yamaguchi 2022, Yoshino 2016). However, a key limitation of much of such research is that it treats justice and punishment merely as survey variables—asking flaming participants whether they felt a sense of justice—without critically examining the underlying psychology or evolutionary logic of these concepts (Kimura 2024a). In contrast, my own research seeks to dig deeper by reinterpreting “justice” and “punishment” through the lens of evolutionary anthropology.

Based on the theoretical discussion above, humans depend on others for information that enhances their fitness. As a result, they are highly sensitive to violations of trust within their ingroup. When ingroup loyalty and respect for tradition (from MFT) are activated, people are prone to strong emotional reactions against behavior they perceive as betrayal, deception, or norm violation—even when the behavior has nothing to do with them personally.

This tendency to punish third parties for violating social expectations is known as “third-party punishment” (Fehr and Fischbacher 2004). I argue that online flaming is a contemporary manifestation of third-party punishment. Moreover, phenomena such as ideological polarization, hate speech, conspiracy theories, and cancel culture reflect deeper conflicts over competing truth defaults, driven by the psychological mechanisms captured by both MFT and SDO.

6.3 What “Contempt for Others” Reveals

SDO describes an attitude that legitimizes intergroup hierarchy, where strong groups dominate weaker ones. It is, in essence, a “top-down” view of group relations, endorsing superiority of one’s own group over others. In contrast, “contempt for others” (a component of VTC) can be seen as a “top-down” view at the interpersonal level—an attitude in which individuals perceive

themselves as superior to others they consider ignorant or unworthy. While the two constructs operate at different social scales (group vs. individual), both share the theme of legitimized superiority.

To justify such contempt, individuals often invoke moral standards or norms—which is where MFT and SDO come into play. These frameworks offer the moral rationale necessary to feel justified in “looking down” on others.

Here, it is important to reiterate that I do not equate “contempt for others” or VTC with the traits originally attributed to the so-called “short-tempered youth” (*kireru wakamono*) discussed by Hayami and others. The full argument is beyond the scope of this paper, but in brief: over Japan’s “Lost 30 Years”, the nation experienced demographic decline (low birth rates) while households increasingly invested in their children, resulting in rising levels of education. Younger generations, especially those born around or after the 1980s (whom I refer to as digital natives), have become highly adept with new technologies.

Yet despite their abilities, these young people—many of whom belong to the so-called “employment ice age generation”—have faced precarious labor markets and stagnant real wages. Against this backdrop, they have developed growing resentment toward older generations and others perceived as beneficiaries of vested privilege.

This is where VTC, MFT, and SDO converge: they help explain why so many people now express strong criticism toward mass media and established elites. This criticism, in turn, fuels the appeal of candidates like Ishimaru and Saitō.

So, what kinds of moral justifications do MFT and SDO offer to VTC-style contempt? Is it simply a matter of constructing a binary between “the internet” and “the mass media” as competing groups, with mass media criticized as a tool of vested power? This is where another important factor enters the picture: the concept of “non-minority politics.”

6.4 The Shift from Non-Minority Politics to Media Criticism: The Underlying Current of the Ishimaru and Saitō Phenomena

As discussed earlier, through years of research analyzing large-scale social data, I identified a pervasive undercurrent in online public opinion in Japan: a critical perspective among self-identified majority groups, who believe that they are not sufficiently benefiting from the system, while socially vulnerable or minority groups are leveraging their marginal status to claim rights and gain advantages. I coined this discourse “non-minority politics.”

In this study, responses to the non-minority politics item were analyzed alongside MFT, SDO, VTC, and CMVI. For independent variables, respondents were classified into four levels—high, mid-high, mid-low, and low—based on the distribution of responses; the average Non-Minority

Politics score, ranging from 1 to 6, was then calculated for each of these levels. As shown in Table 12, those who endorsed non-minority politics tended to score higher on MFT, SDO, contempt for others, self-esteem, and CMVI.

A path analysis (structural equation modeling) was then conducted to investigate the causal relationships among these variables. The resulting models, shown in Figures 2 and 3, offered the best fit for describing these relationships. The numerical values in the path diagrams represent standardized parameter estimates, indicating the effect size of each predictor. For example, a one-point increase in non-minority politics corresponds to a 0.6-point increase in media criticism.

In Figure 2, ingroup loyalty and respect for tradition (MFT), along with SDO, serve as foundational emotional mechanisms that influence individual-level psychosocial traits such as self-esteem, contempt for others, and non-minority politics. These, in turn, strongly contribute to criticism of media elites. Notably, some variables—such as the paths between SDO and self-esteem, or between ingroup loyalty and CMVI—were not statistically significant, which is indicated by dashed lines in the diagrams.

Table 12. Relationship Between Non-Minority Politics and MFT, SDO, VTC, and CMVI

	high	mid-high	mid-low	low
MFT: Respect for Tradition	4.01	3.49	3.15	2.88
MFT: Ingroup Loyalty	4.20	3.46	3.25	2.83
SDO	4.31	3.60	3.19	2.77
Self-Esteem (VTC)	3.76	3.49	3.41	3.20
Contempt for Others (VTC)	4.10	3.52	3.28	2.94
CMVI	3.89	3.33	3.09	2.37

Of particular importance here is the finding that contempt for others and non-minority politics are mutually reinforcing and together exert a powerful influence on CMVI. Additionally, respect for tradition (a subscale of MFT) also plays a significant role.

The “Respect for Tradition” scale includes the following three items:

1. Pride in one's country's history
2. Belief that men and women have distinct roles in society
3. The view that children should be taught to respect national history, tradition, and socially approved figures

These reflect collectivist and conservative values. The average score across respondents was 3.84 (on a 1-6 scale, with a neutral midpoint of 3.5), suggesting generally positive endorsement.

Table 13 shows the average scores of respect for tradition scores by candidate. Based on their distributions, nearly 70% of respondents scored at or above the neutral point, with Koike and Ishimaru exceeding 75%. The highest support came from Tamogami (85.3%), followed closely by

Saitō (84.6%) and Sakurai (84.2%). One noteworthy case is Anno. While his supporters tended to lean liberal and scored relatively low on non-minority politics (second only to Renhō), 82.6% of his supporters endorsed respect for tradition, on average, surpassing even Koike and Ishimaru.

Figure 2. Path Diagram – Tokyo Gubernatorial Election Respondents (N=804)

CFI=0.968, RMSEA=0.088

In the figure, stronger relationships are represented with thicker lines, whereas weaker relationships (with estimated values below 0.2) are depicted with thinner lines.

Figure 3. Path Diagram – Hyogo Gubernatorial Election Respondents (N=585)

CFI=0.968, RMSEA=0.084

In the figure, dashed lines indicate paths not significant at the 5% level. Stronger relationships are represented with thicker lines, whereas weaker relationships (with estimated values below 0.2) are depicted with thinner lines.

Table 13. Average Score of Respect for Tradition (MFT) by Candidate

	N	Average		N	Average
Respondents Total	1678	3.841	Tamogami	34	4.490
Saitō	267	4.201	Sakurai	19	4.404
Shimizu	36	4.028	Himazora	20	4.250
Tachibana	25	4.013	Anno	23	4.072
Inamura	257	3.894	Ishimaru	221	3.991
			Koike	407	3.952
			Renhō	80	3.696

Over the past decade of studying online public opinion, I have come to recognize that the values represented by respect for tradition (as conceptualized in Moral Foundations Theory, MFT) operate with remarkable strength in Japanese society.

Mainstream mass media tends to emphasize diversity and human rights as universal values, often seeking to highlight voices from historically marginalized or disadvantaged groups. However, the present analysis indicates that non-minority politics and respect for tradition, in conjunction with contempt for others, function as key psychological drivers behind strong criticism of the mass media.

This suggests a growing public dissatisfaction that mainstream media does not adequately represent the concerns, struggles, and values of the “non-minority”—those who perceive themselves as part of the majority but feel left behind.

Rather than gravitating toward more extreme figures like Tamogami, Sakurai, or Tachibana, voters may have turned to Ishimaru and Saitō as more relatable figures—candidates who could channel and articulate the frustrations people feel toward the mass media and vested power structures.

As social pluralization, diversification, globalization, and digital networking continue to accelerate, nation-states are being forced to reexamine the foundations of their social cohesion. Historically, mass media has played an indispensable institutional role in shaping and sustaining national values.

Today, however, mass media must find new ways to listen to and elevate not only the values and moral perspectives promoted by vocal actors on social media, but also the silent majority behind them—those whose concerns are rarely heard. It is this capacity to truly amplify the full spectrum of public sentiment that will determine the future relevance and legitimacy of the mass media in democratic societies.

Footnotes

ⁱ The analytical code used in this study was prepared by Mr. Atsushi Yamanaka, a doctoral candidate at the same graduate school. I would like to express my sincere gratitude for his contribution.

ⁱⁱ Japan's "Lost 30 Years" refers to the prolonged period of economic stagnation and deflation that began in the early 1990s following the collapse of Japan's asset price bubble. Despite various fiscal and monetary interventions, Japan struggled to return to robust economic dynamism, and the term "Lost 30 Years" now reflects the enduring structural and psychological impacts on Japanese society and economy.

ⁱⁱⁱ Indeed, by combining social data with generative AI, it is becoming increasingly possible to visualize a multiplicity of voices. This approach is discussed in detail in Chapter 13 of my in-press book (Kimura, in-press).

Acknowledgements

The survey discussed in this article was conducted as part of a project research initiative at the Graduate School of Sociology, Rikkyo University.

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